

Strontium-based Additive for Enhanced Aluminum A356-Reinforced Al₂O₃ Composite Mechanical Properties and Microstructures

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ABSTRACT

A stir-casting process has produced aluminum alloy A356 reinforced with Al₂O₃ metal matrix composites (MMCs). The strontium was added into molten Al A356 to improve the mechanical properties of composites. The strontium used varied from 0.046 wt.% to 0.070 wt.%, while Al₂O₃ was kept constant at 10 vf-%. This research aims to study the effect of Sr on the microstructure and mechanical properties of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite. The A356 was melted at 800°C and mixed with Al-5TiB, Al-5Sr, and Mg as a master alloy of the matrix, then flushed with argon to remove all the gas bubbles from liquid aluminum and stirred for 2 minutes afterward, it was poured with Al₂O₃ particles and stirred again for 3 minutes to distribute the Al₂O₃ particles in molten Al matrix. The composites produced then characterized both microstructural analysis and mechanical properties. The maximum strength, elongation, and hardness of composites were achieved at 0,046 wt.% Sr with the value of 185 MPa, 4.00%, and 45.3 HRB, while strength,

elongation, and hardness of unreinforced were 101 MPa, 2,72%, and 40 HRB respectively and further addition of Sr mechanical properties decreased. The increase in the strength is due to the refinement of Mg₂Si primary in the matrix.

Keywords: Al-A356, Al₂O₃ particles, Sr modification, mechanical properties, stir casting

Statements and Declarations

All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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T.K.S.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **A.Z.:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **R.F.H.H.:** Validation, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision.

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1. Introduction

Composite materials are multiphase materials obtained through the artificial combination of different materials to attain properties that the individual components cannot attain by themselves[1]. Metal matrix composites mostly use aluminum as a matrix because Al is ductile, low-density, and castable. Therefore aluminum composites have high specific strength and specific modulus, good mechanical properties at high temperatures, and good wear resistance[2,3]. Aluminum is generally used because of easy to process and has high ductility. Ductility is essential since the particle used is very hard and brittle. Alumina is used for reinforcement because it has good thermal stability and mechanical properties[4]. However, the ductility of the MMCs deteriorates significantly with high ceramic particle concentration[5–7]. MMCs have become material substitutions for the existing components for automotive and aerospace applications. In this research, aluminum alloy A356 with the primary alloy of Mg and Si is used as a matrix combined with alumina as a reinforced material, and some modifier elements such as TiB and strontium are added. Adding Sr into Al improves the mechanical properties by modifying the microstructure of eutectic Si and Mg₂Si.

Al-Si-Mg is commonly used in industry because it has good strength, high hardness, and good wear resistance[8]. This characteristic is due to the formation of Mg₂Si compound in the form of primary, secondary and tertiary Mg₂Si in the aluminum matrix. Mg₂Si has a high melting temperature of 1085⁰C, a low density of $1,99 \times 10^3 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, a high hardness of $4,5 \times 10^9 \text{ N m}^{-2}$, and a reasonably high elastic modulus of 120 GPa[9,10]. Under normal casting conditions, the microstructure of Al-Mg-Si is generally formed undesirably, and it is also coarse dendritic-like primary Mg₂Si and brittle Chinese script-like secondary Mg₂Si that will affect less mechanical properties as a result. Therefore, there are many ways to avoid the formation of coarse Mg₂Si, such as the shearing process or the addition of certain elements which can modify the shape of Mg₂Si. Some elements that can be used as modifiers are sodium, yttrium, or strontium[11–13]. In this present study, strontium is used to modify the shape of Mg₂Si either in the form of primary or secondary. Furthermore, strontium is widely used as the modifier because of its low fading rate.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Making of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite

Materials used in this experiment were Al A356, Al₅TiB, Al₁₅Sr as the master alloy matrix, and 10 wt.% Mg as a wetting agent. Al A356 and Mg were melted at 800° C (the visualization of Al–Si phase diagram shown in the **Scheme 1**), Al₅TiB and Al₁₅Sr were added into molten aluminum, stirred with a rotational speed of 500 rpm for 3 minutes, and flushed with argon for 1 minute. Al₅TiB is constant at 0.24 wt.% while strontium from Al₁₅Sr varies from 0.01 wt.% to 0.04 wt.%. Alumina particles with 10 vf-% were poured manually into the vortex of master alloy melt after the dross was removed, then stirred for 8 minutes. The composite melts were poured into a tensile test mold. The stir casting apparatus is seen in **Figure 1** and illustrated in **Scheme 2**. The chemical compositions of the alloy prepared are listed in **Table 1**.

Scheme 1. Visualization of Al–Si phase diagram, adapted from the previous studies[14,15].

Figure 1. Stir casting equipment parts, (a) tilt furnace and stirrer, (b) furnace, and (c) Ar gas tube.

Scheme 2. Illustration for the stir casting equipments and its components.

2.2. Characterization of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite

The mechanical properties of composites were measured, including tensile strength, hardness, and porosity. Tensile testing was carried out using GOTECH AI-7000 LA 10 based on ASTM E8M-09. The tensile testing was carried out using three specimens for each variable. Hardness testing was carried out using a Rocky machine with the Rockwell B method based on ASTM E18-11 for each sample, five hardness readings on randomly selected regions were taken to eliminate the segregation effects and get an expected value of the matrix material hardness. The porosity of the composite was measured using the Archimedean method. The samples were furnace-dried to remove any residual moisture. Particular fluids (e.g. water and ethanol) were used as impregnating fluids to study the effect of wettability on fluid absorption. The samples' weights were recorded before and after immersion in the fluids. Porosity was then calculated. Archimedean method is a cost-effective and straightforward method for measuring open porosity, but it does not provide details about pore shape, size, or distribution. The microstructure of composites was analyzed following the metallography procedure. The samples representative was prepared by grinding using emery paper starting from #80, #150, #240, #400, #600, #800, #1000, #1200, to #1500, then polished using alumina powder to remove scratches from grinding process, then etched with 0.5% HF for 1 minute. All preparation samples were observed using OLYMPUS BX41M-LED optical microscope, and further analysis using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) link to Energy Dispersive Spectrum (EDS), and phases content in composites was confirmed by XRD.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite analyzed by Optical Emission Spectroscopy (OES). The composition design was different from the OES result. The Mg content should be 10 wt.% or less; however, the OES measured was 12 wt.%. Moreover, the Sr should be matched to the material balance designed before casting. Even though it is measured stray away from the designed alloy, Ti is close to the design composition, i.e., 0.24 wt.%. It is assumed that the over-reading of the instrument can cause such deviation in measuring the

Mg and Sr content inside the material. Therefore in this study, the composition of Sr inside composites is taken from OES results.

Table 1. Chemical composition of AlA356 and AlA356/Al₂O₃ cast composites.

Composite	Elements (wt.%)						
	Si	Mg	Fe	Cu	Ti	Sr	Al
A356	7.410	0.129	0.162	0.0107	0.131	-	92.1
1	6.720	12.000	11.400	-	-	-	Bal.
2	6.730	12.000	1.250	-	0.210	0.046	Bal.
3	6.790	12.000	1.450	-	0.223	0.050	Bal.
4	6.960	12.000	1.650	-	0.197	0.056	Bal.
5	6.970	12.000	2.100	-	0.209	0.064	Bal.
6	7.120	12.000	1.410	-	0.200	0.070	Bal.

3.1. Effect of Sr on Microstructure of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite

Microstructures of AlA356 and AlA356/Al₂O₃ composites with various Sr addition were observed using an optical microscope, as shown in **Figure 2**. It can be seen that the material has two dominant phases. The white phase is identified as α -Al, the main phase in the aluminum matrix, while the black phase is Al₂O₃ particle reinforcement. The black color is formed because Al₂O₃ is a ceramic material that cannot reflect light and causes the captured image on the microscope to be black. **Figure 2** also showed the different shapes and sizes of a primary Mg₂Si particle. The composites without Sr showed elongation of primary Mg₂Si with a low amount in the matrix phase, as seen in **Figure 2(a)**. The composites with a content of 0.046 wt.% Sr showed the refinement of primary Mg₂Si spacing with a large amount in the aluminum matrix. The modification process of the Mg₂Si occurs in a composite with a higher Sr content, as seen in **Figure 2(e)**. The shape of the primary Mg₂Si changes from long needles to being more globular or compact in the aluminum matrix.

Figure 2. Microstructure of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite with different of strontium (a) 0 wt.%, (b) 0.046 wt.%, (c) 0.050 wt.%, (d) 0.056 wt.%, (e) 0.064 wt.% and (f) 0.070 wt.%. Magnification 200x.

The process of modification and refinement of the primary Mg₂Si particle can occur due to a compound named Al₄Sr formed in the Al matrix. It also occurs in current research for composites with the addition of 0.046 wt.% Sr, which was analyzed further by XRD (**Fig. 3**). Al₄Sr can act as a nucleating agent. Some other phases present are MgAl₂O₄, Al₄Sr, Mg₂Si, and MgAl₂O₄ which are assumed as a reaction product between matrix and reinforced in the interface (**Fig. 4(a)**) and refinement of primary Mg₂Si can be seen in **Figure 4(b)**. A nucleating agent can be developed when the condition is achieved, and the lattice differences or the number of disregistry must be less than 15%[16]. Moreover, Mingbo et al. stated that the disregistry value of Mg₂Si and Al₄Sr compound on the plane (100) was only 0.69%, meaning the nucleation growth can be formed[17]. As an additional explanation, dislocations cause misalignment of atoms across the slip plane, defined by the displacement difference between adjacent atoms. This misalignment, also called disregistry, generates lattice energy and resistance to movement, influenced by atomic forces in the lattice. These forces are balanced by elastic stresses from the crystals above and below the slip plane[18,19].

Figure 3. XRD pattern of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite with 0.046 wt.% Sr.

Table 2. Phases in Al-Mg-Si

Phase	Shape Identification	Color Identification
Aluminum	Base material	White
primary Mg ₂ Si	snowflake / compact	Blue
secondary Mg ₂ Si	Chinese script	Blue
ternary Mg ₂ Si	net-like	Grey, Dark

Figure 4. Microstructure of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite with 0.046 wt.% Sr; a) interface and b) primary Mg₂Si or lamellar Mg-Mg₂Si at room temperature[20].

Hu-Li Tian et al.[21], found that the composite with Al-12.5Mg-7.3Si can produce three types of phases, which are primary Mg₂Si, secondary Al-Mg₂Si, and ternary Al-Mg₂Si-Si while in our observation in **Figure 5** can be seen that the composite with 0.064 wt.% Sr has three phases, which are binary Al-Mg₂Si, ternary Al-Mg₂Si-Si, and primary Mg₂Si which is identified in **Table 2**, where the morphology of Mg₂Si matched with the previous work[22–24].

3.2. Effect of Sr on Primary and Secondary Mg₂Si Particles

Based on the previous research, the refinement mechanism of secondary Mg₂Si is strongly influenced by temperature changes. Undercooling temperature can significantly affect solidification and phase transformation[17]. The previous research conducted by Tebib et al.[25] stated that with the addition of the Sr element, the eutectic temperature would be decreased, so the density of secondary Mg₂Si increases, which will result in the diminution of the size of secondary Mg₂Si, which was also seen in current research for composite with 0.046 wt.% Sr. The mechanism of this refinement of secondary Mg₂Si also occurred because the Sr element could reduce the eutectic temperature (T_g) at which the eutectic process is taking place. With the lower T_g , the undercooling condition can be more remarkable, which causes the phases to be formed relatively smoother, so they can be more refined[26]. The refined phase is closely related to the low number of r^* (r critical), according to **Equation (1)**.

$$r^* = \frac{2\sigma}{\Delta G_r} = \frac{2\sigma \times T_m}{L_m \times \Delta T} \quad (1)$$

Where r^* is the critical nucleus radius, σ is interfacial energy per unit area, T_m is the temperature crystallization occurs, L_m is the latent heat, and ΔT is the amount of undercooling[25,27]. The higher the ΔT , the lower the r^* value, making it possible to form more nuclei, so the density of the secondary Mg₂Si particle formed in the matrix can be increased. Besides, the refinement process may occur because of the low solubility of Sr in aluminum[28]. It causes many Sr elements to be located at the interface of Mg₂Si growth, which can inhibit the growth of the secondary Mg₂Si. Moreover, adding the Sr element may result in refining the secondary Mg₂Si. It can be seen from a distance between lamellar that they become more refined, which also occurred in the current work.

In this study, adding more Sr elements is not always followed by refining and modifying secondary Mg₂Si. The process of refining and modifying occurs in a composite with 0.046 wt.% Sr and 0.064 wt.% Sr, respectively, as seen in **Figure 2(b)** and **2(e)**. To prove that process, the length of the distance between the Mg₂Si binary eutectic, measured two times for each composition, is shown in **Figure 2**. The composites with 0.046 wt.% Sr seen that the spacing between lamellar of Mg₂Si

are 14.6 μm and 25.1 μm which is the finest spacing among other composites, while the composites with 0.050 wt.% Sr are 71.2 μm and 96.9 μm . The spacing between lamellar of Mg_2Si for composites with 0.056 wt.% o Sr is 72.5 μm and 121 μm , while composite with 0.064 wt.% Sr shows less spacing which is 30.9 μm and 35.2 μm and composite with 0.050 wt.% Sr has equal distances which are 55.2 μm and 54.5 nm respectively. The different results can be caused by Sr content in these materials, which do not function appropriately in the process of modifying the secondary Mg_2Si because the Sr could also serve to modify the primary Mg_2Si phase[29] in the form of snowflakes or compact; therefore the effect of Sr on the refinement of Mg_2Si is achieved at composites with 0.046 wt.% Sr and 0.064 wt.% Sr.

Figure 5. Different magnification microstructures of Al A356/ Al_2O_3 composite with 0.64 wt.% Sr show the presence of Mg_2Si phase: a) 200x and b) 500x.

3.3. Effect of Sr on Mechanical Properties of Al A356/ Al_2O_3 composite.

Mechanical properties of unmodified and modified composites are shown in **Figure 6**. **Figure 6(a)** points out the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of Al A356/ Al_2O_3 with various content of wt.% Sr. It is seen that the optimum tensile strength and elongation are 185 MPa and 4%, respectively, found at composite with the addition of 0.046 wt.% Sr. UTS value was generally increased up to particular wt.% Sr concentration compared to without Sr. Generally, all composite material increases strength due to the addition of reinforcing particles Al_2O_3 (alumina) into the aluminum matrix. The refinement of primary Mg_2Si in composites with 0046 wt.% Sr also contributed to the mechanical properties such as strength and hardness. Reinforcing particles help anchor and lock the dislocations. Therefore, slips cannot

occur, making the material have excellent mechanical properties. In addition, the mechanical properties increase is also caused by grain refinement by reinforcement particles. There were considerable differences in grain size between materials with different vol.% of reinforcement. Composite with ~5 vol.% Al₂O₃ has a bigger grain size and is further reduced with higher amount reaching ~10 vol.% Al₂O₃ addition. In the current work, we consider the refinement of Mg₂Si in the aluminum matrix. This result is consistent with the previous study[25]. The conducted for alloy Al-Mg-Si-Cu possessed high mechanical properties with the addition of Sr due to the modification process and refinement of Mg₂Si as discussed in the microstructure.

Figure 6. (a) Tensile strength, (b) elongation, (c) hardness, and (d) porosity as a Mechanical Properties parameter of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite with different Sr.

The highest hardness of 45 HRB was obtained at composite with 0.046 wt.% of Sr (**Fig. 6(c)**). This was expected because of the modification and refinement of Mg₂Si as seen in **Figure 2**. Besides Mg₂Si affecting the mechanical properties of composites, the presence of porosity is also attributed to mechanical properties. Porosity can occur for several reasons, such as raw material, moisture, hydrogen solubility changes due to differences in melting temperature, or the damage of an oxide film layer by the stirring process, causing the molten materials to have direct contact with air[30]. **Figure 6** shows the amount of porosity content in the composite material. It is noticeable that the total composite porosity tends to be lower than the modified composite material. The porosity of the total composite is 4.1%, while the modified composite is between 6-8%. The lowest porosity for

modified composites is achieved at the addition of 0.046 wt.% Sr. Thus, the tensile strength and hardness are also optimum at this composition.

4. Conclusions

The effects of Sr addition on microstructure and mechanical properties of Al A356/Al₂O₃ composite are investigated in this study, and it is concluded as follows:

- i. The microstructure of Al A356/Al₂O₃ consists of primary Mg₂Si, secondary Al-Mg₂Si, and tertiary Al-Mg₂Si-Si.
- ii. The addition of Sr can affect the shape and size of the primary Mg₂Si and the secondary Al-Mg₂Si phases.
- iii. Sr can change the primary Mg₂Si from long needles to be more globular or compact at composites with 0.064 wt.% Sr.
- iv. Sr can refine the Mg₂Si secondary by reducing the spacing between two lamellar obtained at composites with 0.046 wt.% Sr.
- v. Mechanical properties optimum is achieved at composites with 0.046 wt.% Sr, both tensile strength and hardness with the value of 185 MPa and 45 HRB, while elongation and porosity are 4.0% and 6%, respectively.
- vi. The refinement of secondary Mg₂Si generated superior mechanical properties compared with the primary Mg₂Si modification.

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